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EMPHASIS ON NOVEL GRANULATION TECHNOLOGIES: AN OVERVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Granulation is one of the most significant unit maneuvers in the production of pharmaceutical solid oral dosage forms. Granulation process imparts improvement in flow and compression characteristic, decreases isolation, improves content uniformity, and avoids excessive fines. The results will be improved yields, reduced tablet defects, increased productivity, and reduced down time. A pharmaceutical organization employs different techniques such as direct-compressing, wet-granulation, or dry granulation methods for the production of pharmaceutical products. The method of selection depends on the ingredients individual characteristics and ability to properly flow, compresses, eject, and disintegrate. Proper granulation process requires thorough knowledge of each ingredient in the formula, the combination of ingredients, and how they work with each other.

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Introduction

Granulation is one of the most significant unit maneuvers in the production of pharmaceutical solid oral dosage forms. Granulation is the process in which primary powder particles are made to adhere to form larger, multiparticle aggregates called granules. Pharmaceutical granules usually made in the size range of from 0.2 to 4.0 mm, depending on their subsequent application. After granulation process, the granules will either be packed (when used as a dosage form, example: Powder form), or they may be mixed with other excipients prior to tablet compression or capsule filling. G

ranulation is mainly used to improve the flow properties of powders and compressibility of powders, and to prevent segregation of blend components.¹

Rationale for granulation:²

- To improve the compaction characteristic of the mix
- To improve the flow properties of the mix
- To prevent the segregation of the constituents of the powder mix.
- Granules being denser than the parent powder mix, occupies less volume per unit weight. They are more convenient for storage and shipment.
- Materials which are slightly hygroscopic may adhere and form a cake if stored as powder. Granulation may reduce this hazard as the granules will absorb some moisture and yet retains their flowability because of their size.
- The granulation of toxic materials will reduce the hazards associated with the generation of toxic dust which may arise when handling powders during the formation of granules.

Granulation method can be majorly classified into two types: Wet granulation and Dry granulation.

Wet granulation is the mainstream granulation technology in production of oral solid dosage forms, because direct compression technique is not the most suitable method for many active pharmaceutical ingredients that are in high dosages or in fine powder form. If ever the active ingredient is sensitive to hydrolysis, it is eliminated by novel

equipment, e.g. in a fluidized bed, which eliminates all problems of wet granulation.³

Essential properties of granules:⁴

Granules should have

- Spherical shape
- Smaller size particle size distribution with sufficient fines to fill void spaces between granules.
- Optimum moisture content (1-2 %)
- Good flow
- Good compressibility
- Sufficient hardness

Factors that governs the formation of effective granules:⁵

- ❖ Particle size of the drug and excipients
- ❖ Type of binder (strong or weak)
- ❖ Volume of binder (less or more)
- ❖ Wet massing time (less or more)
- ❖ Amount of shear applied
- ❖ Drying rate (Hydrate formation and polymorphism)

NOVEL GRANULATION TECHNOLOGIES ARE:

1) Pneumatic Dry Granulation (PDG):^{6,7}

The PDG TechnologyTM:

- It can produce porous granules with excellent compressibility and flowability properties.
- It works on the basis of pneumatic dry granulation principle, a novel dry method for automatic or semiautomatic production of granules,
- It enables flexible modification of processing variables such as drug load, disintegration time and tablet hardness,
- It is possible to achieve:
 - ✓ Incorporation of high dose drugs, even with 'difficult' APIs and combination formulas
 - ✓ Taste masking
 - ✓ Excellent stability
 - ✓ It is compatible with other techniques, such as sustained release, fast release, etc.
 - ✓ It is the matter of more number of patent applications and
- It is suitable for thermosensitive and moisture sensitive drugs.

Granulation process:

The PDG process can apply to produce the granules of any pharmaceutical solid dosage ingredient. The granules obtained are with excellent compressibility and flowability characteristics. The PDG method enables to develop controlled release, fast release, fixed dose, and oral disintegrating tablets with excellent results.⁸

Now-a-days the wet granulation is most widely and commonly used granulation process. During the granulation process, formulation scientists usually prefer a direct compression or dry granulation method. But in most of the cases, they wind-up with a wet granulation formulation due to the processing problems.

Figure 1: Comparison of PDG technology and Wet granulation process

Wet granulation is also incompatible in terms of economic line and for moisture sensitive and heat sensitive active principles. It utilizes large number of labours and long duration of time. Additionally, includes shortcomings such as several number of stages and each stage necessitates qualification, cleaning, and cleaning validation, huge loss of ingredients occurs during the transfer between the stages. Due to these demerits, scale up is necessary which is an issue and requires a considerable investment.⁹

The PDG technology produced granules have excellent characteristics which were equivalent in a number of ways to those produced by either conventional wet granulation or dry granulation methods and which were much better than the

powder blend from the direct compression formulation. Additional key advantages includes high drug load, faster speed of manufacturing of granules and tablets, safety in terms of closed systems, stable end products, bypassing the scale-up and potential fast disintegrating properties for granules and tablets. Such potential results can be achieved which eliminate the cost of drying wet granulations while producing materials which have similar needed properties, and save the investment in procuring specialized equipment for dry granulation.¹⁰

2) Foamed Binder Technology:

The credentials for the development of novel foamed binder technology deserves for The Dow Chemical Company can help to achieve faster, simpler, and safer wet granulation processing.¹¹ The formulation scientists of Dow Chemical Company have proven the binder distribution in the formulation material using METHOCEL polymers and resulted with excellent processing advantages.¹² When compared to traditional spray processing, this novel technology offers shorten processing times by reducing water requirements. It can speed up granulation processing and improve reproducibility through more uniform binder distribution. In spite of that, it avoids usage of spray nozzles and their many variables in granulation processing equipment. Foam processing also offers better end point determinations and reduced equipment clean-up time.

Foamed binder processing offers many key advantages, doesn't demand new equipment or radical changes in processing techniques. It can very easily use it with familiar high shear, low shear, or fluid bed granulation equipment, in both laboratory- and large-scale production.¹³

Mechanism of foam binder granulation:

Foam granulation works by mechanism of tremendous increase in the liquid surface area and volume of polymeric binder foams to improve the distribution of the water/binder system throughout the powder bed of a solid dose pharmaceutical formulation. Foam can be generated with consistency like shaving cream, using simple foam generation apparatus for conventional water-soluble excipient binder such as hydroxypropyl

methylcellulose (METHOCEL Hypromellose). Owing to excellent stable film forming property of Hypromellose polymers made ideal candidates for this technology.

The potential advantage of this technique is, the foam generator can be connected directly to high-shear, low-shear, or fluid bed granulation equipment for small-scale laboratory production as well as large scale production.¹⁴

Binding capacity and particle coverage

The effectiveness of foam binder performance is rapid and extremely efficient particle coverage. When compared to sprayed liquid binders, foam binders provide much higher surface area and very rapid spreadability over powder surfaces in even fashion. The foamed binders and powder particles show superior mutual flow through one another.

The foam binder exhibits a low soak: spread ratio, so particle surfaces are quickly and completely covered. In contrast to spraying, it is a cumulative process that begins with small liquid droplets "dappling" particle surfaces until sufficient binder liquid accumulates to initiate particle agglomeration. Spraying requires relatively more water and processing time than a foamed binder to achieve particle agglomeration.

The foam binder technology also eliminates the usage of spray nozzles and their variables, such as nozzle configuration, distance from the moving powder bed, spray patterns, clogging, droplet size, and droplet distribution. The dilute binder solutions are easy to handle in processing. Overall, foam binder processing is easier, faster, and allows safer handling of potent drug compounds.¹⁵

3) Freeze Granulation Technology:

The credentials for development of this novel alternate technique reserves for Swedish Ceramic Institute (SCI).¹⁶ This type of granulation enables production of dry granules from suspension. Here the mechanism of granulation includes powder suspension is sprayed into liquid nitrogen and the drops (granules) are instantaneously frozen. Subsequently the granules are dried by sublimation of the ice without any segregation effects as in the case of traditional drying in air.

Figure 2: Freeze granulation process

The resulting granules will be spherical free flowing with optimal homogeneity.¹⁷

In spite of high degree of homogeneity freeze granulation offers several advantages:¹⁸

- It regulates the density of granules by the solid content of the suspension.
- Serious oxidation of non-oxides and metals are prevented as there is mild drying.
- No cavities in the granules.
- Very high yield of material is obtained.
- Possibility of recycling of organic solvents.
- Easy to clean the equipment.
- Reproducibility in production small (50-100 ml suspension) and large quantities of granules

4) Melt Granulation Technology:

This technology is also called as thermoplastic granulation or melt agglomeration as the granules are obtained by the addition of either a molten binder or solid binder which melts during the process.

Principle: The process of granulation consists of combination of three phases:

- I. Wetting and nucleation
- II. Coalescence step
- III. Attrition and breakage

Wetting and nucleation step

In this step, the binder comes in contact with the powder bed and liquid bridge is formed, leading to the formation of small aggregates.

Schafer and Mathiesen were proposed two nucleation mechanisms: immersion and distribution.

Immersion

Nucleation by immersion occurs when the size of the molten binder droplets is bigger than that of the fine solid particles. Immersion is followed by deposition of fine solid particles onto the surface of molten binder droplets.

Figure 3: Mechanism of melt granulation: Immersion

Distribution

In this method, a molten binding liquid is spread onto the surface of fine solid surfaces. This is followed by the formation of nuclei by the collision of the wet particles. Generally, some favorable conditions such as small binder droplet size, low binder viscosity and high shearing forces are necessary for nucleation.

Figure 4: Mechanism of melt granulation: Distribution

Coalescence step

The nuclei having residual surface liquid leads to the successful fusion of nuclei. The surface liquid contributes plasticity to the nuclei and which is requisite for the deformation of nuclei surface for coalescence as well as for the promotion of spherical shape of granules.

Attrition-breaking step

It is related to formation of granular fractures which are solidified by tray cooling to ambient temperature without drying using tumbling process. Consequently, breakage plays key role in affecting the resultant properties of the melt granules during the granulation phase.

Requirements of melt granulation:

- Usually, melttable binder at a concentration of 10-30% w/w, with respect to the fine solid excipients is used.
- The melttable binder should have the melting in the range of 50-100° C.
- Hydrophilic melttable binders are employed to produce immediate release formulations, while hydrophobic melttable binders are preferred for prolonged release formulations.
- The melting point of other fine solid excipients should be at least 20° C higher than that of maximum processing temperature.

Ideal characters of melttable binder:

- It must be solid at room temperature and melt within the range of 40-80° C.
- It should be physically and chemically stable.
- Its hydrophilic lipophilic balance (HLB) value must ensure the correct release of the API.

Advantages of melt granulation:

- ✓ Neither of solvent nor water is used.
- ✓ Less number of simple processing steps are needed and hence time consuming in drying step is avoided.
- ✓ Uniform dispersion of fine particle occurs.
- ✓ Good stability at different pH and moisture level.

- ✓ As they are non-swellable and water insoluble in nature can be used safely in humans.

The significant advantage of melt granulation is that the use of various choices of the granulation excipients which may enable the formulator to manipulate the drug dissolution rate from the corresponding dosage form.¹⁹

5) Granurex® Technology:

The Granurex® technology performs both coating and powder layering processes (Figure 5). The Vector Corporation demonstrated the multiple coating and powder (ingredient) layers with accuracy and operation control of a Granurex® rotor processor.

Figure 5: Granurex® Technology: Precision coating and powder layering Processes

Key feature:

Unique, efficient granulation processes:

Granules produced by the Granurex® are dense and spherical in shape. The Vector Corporation demonstrated that the Granurex® processes of Ciprofloxacin from a 7 µm poorly flowing powder to 200 µm granules with excellent flow characteristics.

One pot processing: A patented feature of the granulator Granurex® (Figure 6) is having unique ability to dry product within the same processing chamber. This unique drying method, combined with 12 bar construction, provides a true one-pot system, ideal for manufacturing highly potent and expensive pharmaceutical compounds.

Figure 6: Onepot processing

Increased batch capacities: In comparison to traditional rotor processors, the patented conical rotor plate (Figure 6) has tremendous capacity in increasing the batch capacity. The designed machine contains the product within the processing area and the peripheral spray guns are embedded into the product, which provides accurate coating with minimal spraying defects.

Figure 7 : Increased batch capacities

Maximum process flexibility: The Corporation has demonstrated maximum process flexibility using micronized acetaminophen as the base material; the Granurex® produced both a 100

μm granulation and a 200 μm spherical bead. In both of the examples, the acetaminophen core material had the same initial Mean Particle Size (X50) of 40 μm .²⁰

6) Fluidized Bed Wet Granulation Process for Solid dispersions:

Classical methods of preparing solid dispersion formulations are the melting method and solvent evaporation techniques. The melting processes require often high temperatures $> 100^{\circ}\text{C}$ which may lead to thermal degradation of the drug substance.

Melt extrusion process has advantage here an attractive, solvent-free solution to extrude polymers together with dissolved drugs homogeneously at much lower temperatures than the melting point of the drug and the softening temperature of the polymer.

While hot melt extrusion processes have been recently recommended for making solid dispersions, solvent based processes had been described in reviews in the past as rather unfavorable with respect to the use of large volumes of organic solvents and related environmental aspects. Novel techniques, fast evaporation technologies (e.g. spray-drying), adopted in big pharmaceutical companies for manufacturing solid dispersions which has been well established in food industry long time before.

Solvent evaporation technologies

Generally solvent evaporation technology requires the following aspects to prepare a solid dispersion:

- Sufficient solubility or swelling of the drug substance and the polymer in the solvent system to allow reasonable low solvent volumes and result in the formation of (molecular) fine dispersion
- Low boiling points of the solvent mixtures to reduce the thermal stress during manufacture and facilitate solvent removal. Solvents act as plasticizers in solid dispersions and increase molecular mobility. Therefore low residual solvent amounts increase the physical stability.

- Low feed viscosities (< 200 mPas) to facilitate its atomization for spraying technologies.
- Careful choice of solvent mixtures: In mixtures, the solvent with the lowest boiling point starts to evaporate first and lead to deterioration in the solubilization power of the remaining solvent mixture. In case of azeotropic mixtures, the constant boiling point during the evaporation process, residual amounts of the solvent with the low boiling points remain higher, fostering molecular mobility and recrystallization potential.
- The applied product temperature and its duration need to be carefully balanced by selecting the most appropriate evaporation technology to produce a chemically and physically stable solid dispersion.

According to the ICH guideline, generally all solvents should be removed to the extent possible to meet product specifications which need to be supported by safety data. Class 2 solvents [e.g., Chloroform: 60 ppm concentration limit (Permissible daily exposure: 0.6 mg/day) and Dichloromethane: 600 ppm concentration limit (Permissible daily exposure: 6 mg/day)] with less severe toxicity should be limited with to protect patients from adverse effects.

Solid dispersions were prepared traditionally decades ago in a rotary evaporator apparatus under reduced pressure. The demerit of this technology is that the dispersion becomes more and more viscous during the evaporation process which hampers or prevents further removal of residual solvents.

Since two to three decades, there was significant innovation with the introduction of carrier gas (e.g. Nitrogen) driven spraying/drying technologies in the pharmaceutical production, e.g. spray drying or spray granulation. A variety of equipment manufacturers launched various kinds of processors with different options and multiple applications.

Comparison of different process gas based, fast solvent evaporation technologies

The 3 different process gas based solvent evaporation technologies were applied to prepare

solid dispersions to assess the feasibility of spraying process. In all three cases the same organic feed solution with 10 % polymer content was used. For the two fluidbed granulation processes inert filler was used in addition (e.g. Lactose, Mannitol). The technologies applied were:

- Classical spray drying
- Fluid-bed granulation top-spray mode
- Fluid-bed granulation bottom-spray mode (with a modified distributor plate)

The following differences were observed regarding processability and the quality of the products obtained from the spraying processes:

- Significant longer process time for the spray drying technology compared to the fluid-bed granulation processes
- Significant higher thermal stress for the spray drying process
- Process air volumes were much higher for the two spray granulations
- Generally larger fine particle fractions in the spray drying process compared to both fluid-bed granulations.
- Bulk densities were low in all cases (ca. 0.2 g/ml) except with the modified spray granulator.²¹

7) Steam Granulation

- It is modified process of wet granulation. As title indicated steam is used as a binder instead of water.
- In this method, the granules are formed by the injection of the required amount of liquid in the form of steam.
- This type of steam injection method, discharges steam at a temperature of about 150° C., tends to cause local overheating and excessive wetting of the particles in the vicinity of the steam nozzles, thereby leads to formation of lumps in the granulated product.²²

Advantages:

- Higher distribution uniformity,
- Higher diffusion rate into powders,
- Steam granules are more spherical,

- Have large surface area hence increased dissolution rate of the drug from granules,
- Processing time is shorter therefore more number of tablets are produced per batch,
- Compared to the use of organic solvent water vapor is environmentally friendly,

8) Thermal Adhesion Granulation Process (TAGP)

It is applicable for preparing direct tableting formulations. TAGP is performed under low moisture content or low content of pharmaceutical acceptable solvent in a mixture containing one or more diluents and/or active ingredients; a binder; and optionally a disintegrant. The process is carried out by heating the mixture at a temperature in the range from 30⁰ C to 130⁰ C in a closed system under mixing by tumble rotation until the formation of granules. In this method less water or solvent used than in traditional granulation.^{23,24} It imparts the granules with significant characteristic features like good flow properties and binding capacity to form the tablet of low friability, adequate hardness and high uptake for active substance whose tableting is poor.

In this process, granules are formed during the moist powder under continuous tumble rotation, as the heated powder mass flows with in the container and agglomerates with the aid of the binder. Drying and milling to form the desired granules are unnecessary in the present invention due to the low amount of moisture introduced to the tableting mixture.

Major advantage of granulating the pharmaceutical product in the closed system is that it helps to minimize the generation of the dust during the processing. This technique serves to contain fine powder active ingredients whose spread or loss from the system is not desirable due to their cost or biological activity.²⁵

9) Moisture Activated Dry Granulation (MADG)

A novel granulation method called moisture-activated dry granulation was developed and reported by Ullah et al.²⁶

- The MADG consists of two steps: wet agglomeration of the tableting powder blend followed by moisture absorption step.

- In this method MADG uses a minimum amount of liquid to activate a binder added as a dry powder, which in turn facilitates particle growth i.e., granules. This is the agglomeration step. Finally, a water-insoluble material such as microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) is then added to absorb any excess moisture so that the resultant granulation does not require a drying step.
- Procedure:
 - Minute quantity of water (1-4%) is added to the tableting powder containing API, binder,

and excipient to form agglomerates. Moisture absorbing material such as MCC and potato starch is then added to absorb any excessive moisture.

- Lubricant is added to above blend. The resultant mixture obtained after addition of lubricant can be compressed directly into tablet.

MCC, potato starch or a mixture of 50% each can be used as moisture absorbing material.

Figure 8: Flow diagram of moisture activated dry granulation process

Figure 8: Flow diagram of moisture activated dry granulation process

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Aniruddha et.al.,²⁷ have evaluated and compared the moist granulation technique to conventional methods using acetaminophen as the model drug for the preparation of immediate release tablets. Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) and MCC served as the binder and moisture-absorbing material, respectively. Water was used as the granulating fluid. They compared the MGT with direct compression and wet granulation methods with sieve analysis (particle size) and density measurements. Moist granulation yielded an increase in particle size compared to direct compression. These results are comparable to those from the traditional wet granulation after drying and screening. Based on the results of particle size, moist granulation suits to conventional wet granulation for this formula. The moist granulation technique appears to have potential for the development of controlled-release formulations.

10. Spheronization^{28,29}

Spheronization also known as Marumerization. The credentials for development of this technique reserved for Caleva Process Solutions Ltd, UK. It is the process where pellets (size from about 0.5 to 2.0 mm) are produced from mixtures of solids and liquids by the involvement of forming and shaping forces. During this process, extrudates are shaped into rounded or spherical granules. This process was first reported by Reynolds and by Conine and Hadley in 1970.

Advantages of spheronisation relevant to pharmaceutical industries

- Easy to coat
- Separation of incompatible drugs
- Ability to mix pellets with different release rates
- Reduced risk of dose dumping
- Reduced risk of local irritation in the gastro-intestinal tract
- Less variable bio-availability

- Particles of 1mm or less behave more like liquids in terms of gastric emptying
- Even distribution over the gastro-intestinal tract.

Process:

Mixing

The ingredients are generally mixed in either a high-shear granulator or a more simple planetary mixer.

Extrusion

The extrusion of the materials is a necessary step prior to spheronization. The size of the spheres is governed by the diameter of the extrudate used for the spheronization process. In a spheronizer, it is possible to obtain spheres with a diameter ranging from about 0.5 mm to 2 mm.

Spheronisation

The ongoing action of particles colliding with the wall and being thrown back to the inside of the plate creates a "rope-like" movement of product along the bowl wall. The continuous collisions of the particles with the wall and with the friction plate gradually turn the cylindrical segments into spheres, provided that the granules are plastic enough to allow the deformation without being destroyed. When the particles attained the desired spherical shape, the discharge valve of the chamber is opened and the granules (pellets) are discharged by the centrifugal force. The design principle of the spheronizer is relatively simple but additions and adaptations are possibility to change bowl sizes according to the requirements for the development of different batch sizes.

Drying

Pellets are dried in a fluid bed drier.

CONCLUSION

This review article majorly focuses on the innovative granulation techniques to produce granules and pellets. Each technology has its own merits and demerits. Selection of method mainly depends on the ingredient's individual characteristics, sufficient flow properly, compresses, eject, and disintegrate. Proper granulation process necessarily uses the knowledge

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of each ingredient in the formula, the combination of ingredients, and how they work with each other.

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